

Steric Effects on Oxymercuration : Oxymercuration-Demercuration of Taraxasteryl, Pseudo-Taraxasteryl, and 19-Epi-Taraxasteryl Acetates[†]

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Contrary to usual expectation, taraxasteryl acetate (1b) and pseudo-taraxasteryl acetate (2b) were found to be totally insensitive to normal oxymercuration. This has been rationalised as being due to the steric effects of the 19- and 17-methyl groups on the formation of intermediate mercurium ions, and on the nucleophile attacking these species. Conformational analysis of 1b shows that its ring E is not a normal chair, but assumes a twisted conformation due to severe nonbonded interaction between the 12-methylene and the 19-methyl group. Both 1b and 2b, however, underwent oxymercuration-demercuration with allylic rearrangement to give the same compound 2c, when heated with Hg(OAc)₂ in glacial HOAc. A partial synthesis of 19-*epi*-taraxasteryl acetate (1d) has been achieved by Wittig reaction on the 19-*epi*-norketone (4b) formed by base-catalysed epimerisation of 4a which in turn was derived from 1b. The steric effects providing the driving force for this unconventional epimerisation of 4a to 4b have been explained and supported by comparative ¹³C nmr spectral analysis of 4a and 4b. Unlike 1b and 2b, 19-*epi*-taraxasteryl acetate (1d) underwent normal oxymercuration. The stereochemical aspect of this reaction has been discussed.

OXYMERCURATION-demercuration of cyclic and acyclic olefins leading to addition across the double bond is a well known reaction¹. It has been assumed^{2,3} that the reaction is initiated by a rapid equilibration of the olefin (a) with an unstable mercurium ion (b), followed by rate- and product-determining attack by a nucleophile X^e (Scheme I). Reductive demercuration of the resultant adduct (c) gives the final product often with

predictable stereoselectivity. Based on this premise it would be interesting to study the steric effects of appropriate functional groups in the olefinic substrates, which might retard or inhibit the preequilibrium formation of the species b, or which, in cases where rapid equilibration is ensured, are expected to govern the stereochemical profile of the final addi-

tion products. The results of oxymercuration-demercuration of several substituted methylenecyclohexanes reported recently by Senda *et al*⁴ have provided some useful information regarding the stereochemistry of this reaction. The stereochemical aspects of this reaction in a methylene *trans*-octalin system is reflected in the products with (-)- γ -cadinene⁴ bearing an exocyclic methylene and a trisubstituted endocyclic double bond.

In course of our chemical investigation of the Indian medicinal plant, *Launaea nudicaulis*⁵, we have been able to isolate, in fairly good yield, the pentacyclic triterpene, taraxasterol (1a) bearing a methylenecyclohexane moiety. Acid-catalysed isomerisation⁶ of 1a afforded pseudotaraxasterol (2a) possessing a trisubstituted endocyclic double bond. Individually these two compounds contain one or the other type of olefinic functions present in γ -cadinene, but differ essentially from the latter by having an equatorial methyl group β to the double bond, and thus offer themselves as two interesting olefinic substrates for studying the stereochemical aspects of oxymercuration. Accordingly, taraxasteryl acetate (1b) and pseudo-taraxasteryl acetate (2b) were separately treated with mercuric acetate in THF at ambient temperature and the resultant reaction mixture in each case was then treated with alkaline sodium borohydride. Contrary to expectation, it was found that both 1b and 2b were totally unreactive to mercuric acetate as indicated by their almost quantitative recovery from the worked-up reaction mixture. Carrying out the reaction for a longer period or

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under refluxing condition also failed to bring about any change in 1b and 2b. However, when 1b and 2b were treated with mercuric acetate in glacial acetic acid under reflux, both afforded the same compound A, $C_{34}H_{54}O_4$ (M^+526), m.p. 242° , $[\alpha]_D +66.9^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), with concomitant precipitation of metallic mercury. Compound A shows in its ir spectrum bands at 1220, 1240 and 1735 cm^{-1} (OAc). The 1H nmr spectrum of the compound shows the presence of two acetoxy groups (δ 2.05, 6H, s). That one of these is associated with a primary allyl

acetate moiety of the type

$$\begin{array}{c} | \\ H_2C \\ | \\ H-C=C-CH_2OAc \\ | \\ -CH \\ | \end{array}$$

is indicated by the appearance of a one-proton multiplet at δ 5.6 and a two-proton AB-quartet at δ -4.5

($J=10\text{ Hz}$). An one-proton multiplet obscured in the above AB-quartet establishes the secondary nature of the other acetoxy function. On the basis of these spectral data and its characteristic mass fragmentation⁷, structure 2c was assigned to compound A.

Mechanistically, the formation of 2c from both 1b and 2b may be assumed to be initiated by the generation of the mercurated species d (from 1b) and e (from 2b). Subsequent demercuration of both d and e with concomitant allylic rearrangement gives the same mesomeric cation f (Scheme II, as indicated by $\curvearrowright$). The latter reacts with acetate anion to give the final product 2c. An intramolecular acetoxylation with simultaneous demercuration (as indicated by $\curvearrowright$ in d and e) may also be considered as a possible alternative route to 2c.

The total insensitivity of **1b** towards normal oxymercuration may be explained by a prior conformational analysis of the compound. Construction of Dreiding model shows that **1b** cannot have a normal chair conformation of its ring E (as in **5**) due to severe steric interaction of the 19-methyl group with the 12-methylene. The presence of such steric strain was also indicated by the chemical shift of the 19-methyl carbon of **1b** and some of its derivatives⁵. This should result in considerable deformation of ring E which would be expected to assume a twisted conformation as shown in **6**. It is believed that **1b** would react with mercuric acetate in this conformation. An examination of the steric effects of the 17- and 19-methyl groups on the two possible transition states leading to the α - and β -mercurium ions **7a** and **7b**, respectively, and on the subsequent attack by nucleophile on these species would probably account for this unusual behaviour of **1b**. It is difficult to conceive the formation of a β -mercurium ion **7b** due to its severe interaction with the 17-methyl group, although attack by a nucleophile on this species from the α -side is free from any appreciable steric interference. On the other hand, the approach of a nucleophile from the β -side on the α -mercurium ion **7a**, assumed to be formed relatively slowly due to some steric effect of the 19-methyl, is prevented by the steric hindrance offered by the 17-methyl group. The net effect would therefore be the observed nonreactivity of **1b** towards oxymercuration. A similar explanation would also apply for the identical behaviour of **2b**.

With a view to establishing the validity of the above conclusion it was decided to study oxymercuration-demercuration on 19-*epi*-taraxasteryl acetate (**1d**) which would be expected to have a normal chair conformation of its E ring (as in **8**) due to the absence of any steric strain between 12-methylene and 19-methyl groups. Consideration of the steric effects in **1d** shows that it should undergo facile oxymercuration. Accordingly, **1d** was prepared from **1b** by the following sequence of reactions. Treatment of **1b** with OsO₄ following the method^{6a} used earlier for structurally similar compound afforded a mixture of two epimeric triols, one of which being formed in large excess over the other. The more polar major triol, C₃₀H₅₂O₃ (M⁺ 460), m.p. 260° [ν_{max} 3400 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ_{ppm} 3.35, 2H, AB q (—C—CH₂OH) and 3.15, 1H, m (>CHOH)] and the less polar minor isomer, m.p. 223° [ν_{max} 3400 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ_{ppm} 3.55, 2H, ill-resolved AB q (—C—CH₂OH) and 3.2, 1H, m (>CHOH)] were assigned the structures **3a** and **3b**, respectively, on the basis of their various spectral data including those of their mass and the ¹³C nmr of 3,30-O, O-diacetyl derivative (**B**) of the major triol (Table 1). The stereochemical assignments of the triols are based on a consideration of the stereochemistry of the intermediate osmic esters. It is interesting to

note that the earlier workers^{6a} reported the formation of a single product in the above reaction of a structurally similar compound.

TABLE 1—CARBON SHIFTS^a OF **4a**, **4b** AND COMPOUND **B**

	4a	4b	Compound B		4a	4b	Compound B
C-1	38.7	38.6	38.2	C-17	34.1	34.5	35.4
C-2	27.3	27.5	23.6	C-18	49.8	49.5	47.2
C-3	78.8	78.5	80.9	C-19	46.0	45.2	40.8
C-4	38.9 ^b	38.7 ^b	38.0 ^b	C-20	218.0	216.0	78.51
C-5	55.3	55.2	55.1	C-21	33.1	33.6	28.3
C-6	18.2	18.2	18.1	C-22	36.3	34.6	39.3
C-7	33.9	33.8	34.2	C-23	27.9	27.9	27.8
C-8	40.8	40.7	41.2	C-24	16.8 ^a	17.0 ^a	16.4 ^d
C-9	50.3	50.1	49.2	C-25	15.8 ^a	15.8 ^a	16.2 ^d
C-10	37.0 ^b	36.9 ^b	36.8 ^b	C-26	16.2 ^a	16.1 ^a	14.6
C-11	21.1	20.8	21.4	C-27	14.5	14.3	20.9
C-12	25.6 ^c	23.9	26.4 ^c	C-28	21.8	17.8	18.4
C-13	37.5	37.0	38.8	C-29	15.3	14.7	65.08
C-14	41.7	41.2	42.9	C-30	—	—	—
				O			170.8
							171.5
C-15	26.5 ^c	26.5	27.8 ^c	-O-C-CH ₃	—	—	—
							21.2
				O			
C-16	36.0	34.8	37.6	-O-C-CH ₃	—	—	—

a—values are in ppm downfield from TMS ;
 $\delta_{(TMS)} = \delta_{(CDCl_3)} + 76.9 ppm$

a,b,c,d—values bearing the same superscript may be interchanged.

Periodate oxidation of both **3a** and **3b** afforded the noraketone, C₂₉H₄₈O₂ (M⁺: 428), m.p. 262°, [α]_D²⁰ + 59.43° (CHCl₃), which from its ir [ν_{max} 33.80 (OH) and 1700 (>C=O) cm⁻¹]. pmr [δ_{ppm} 3.15, 1H, m (>CHOH), 2.40, 3H, m and 1.1, 3H, d,

O
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J=7 Hz (Me-CH-C-CH₂-CH₂-)] and mass spectral data was shown to have the structure **4a**. The ¹³C nmr spectrum of the compound (Table 1) is also in accord with this structure.

The next step in the proposed partial synthesis of **1d** involved the base-catalysed isomerisation of **4a** to its C-19 epimer **4b**. From a naive consideration of thermodynamic stability, such epimerisation would seem to be impossible since in absence of other compelling factors cyclohexanones with an equatorial α -methyl is thermodynamically more stable than its isomer bearing an axial methyl at the α -position. The unique feature of steric interactions existing in **4a** fortunately helped to reverse the direction of epimerisation in the most unconventional manner to give the 19-*epi*-noraketone **4b**. A convincing rationale for this unprecedented transformation emerges from a comparison of the significant nonbonded interactions present in the C, D and E rings of **4a** and **4b** as shown in their conformational expressions **10a** and **10b**, respectively (Scheme III). In **10a** the interactions between the 19-methyl and the 12-methylene and the carbonyl group (at C-20) taken together are clearly greater than the 1,3-diaxial interaction between the 17- and 19-methyl groups in **10b**, and this actually provides

the driving force for the conversion of **4a** to **4b**. Thus adsorption of **4a** on basic alumina^{9a} followed by elution of the material after 3 days afforded an equilibrium mixture of **4a** and **4b** in a ratio of about 60 : 40. The same could be achieved by treatment of **4a** with ethanolic alkali or with sodium methoxide in dry methanol. The product obtained as a microcrystalline solid after repeated crystallisations from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 242°, showed a single iodine-staining spot on thin-layer chromatograms run in different solvent systems, and had the same R_f value as that of the starting material. Although it was initially thought to be a pure sample of the isomeric norketone **4b** from a comparison of its physical constants, ir, pmr and mass spectral data with those of **4a**, a ^{13}C nmr spectral analysis of the isomerised product clearly indicated the presence of **4a** as a minor component in this material. Comparison of the ^{13}C nmr spectrum of this reaction product with that of pure **4a** shows that the former contains two sets of signals, one of which corresponds to the carbon atoms of pure **4a**. The additional signals (Table 1) must therefore be due to the carbon atoms of a new compound which has most of its carbon resonances almost coinciding with those of **4a**. The essential differences in the carbon shifts of pure **4a** and those of the pure isomerised product **4b**, as obtained by the above subtraction process, may be well accounted for in terms of the changed additivity parameters attendant with epimerisation at C-19 of **4a** producing 19-*epi*-

norketone **4b** ($10a \rightleftharpoons 10b$).^{9a} Thus the release of the steric strain between the 12-methylene and the equatorial 19-methyl group (C-29) in **4a** owing to latter changing to **4b** (with an axial 19-methyl group) is accompanied by an expected downfield shift of C-12 of **4b** by 1.7 ppm. A corresponding deshielding of the 19-methyl carbon (C-29) of **4b** is, however, not observed due to a newly generated shielding effect arising out of the 1 : 3-diaxial interaction between the 17- and 19-methyl groups of **4b**. But this interaction in turn has resulted in the expected shielding of C-28 (17-methyl) of **4b** by 4 ppm (Table 1). These spectral data thus strongly support the structure of the isomeric product to be the C-19 epimer of **4a**. But all attempts to isolate **4b** in the pure state by repeated fractional crystallisations of the mixture from different solvents or by repeated column chromatography and even by carrying out these processes on the acetylated mixture were unsuccessful. So the above mixture of **4a** and **4b** were subjected to Wittig reaction with the ylid prepared from methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide in presence of NaH in DMSO. This has yielded a mixture of two triterpenoids in extremely poor yield. One of these was identified with taraxasterol (**1a**) while the other, separated from **1a** by repeated column chromatography, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ (M^+ 426), was shown to be the desired 19-*epi*-taraxasterol (**1c**) from its pmr and mass spectral data which were strikingly similar to those of **1a**. The acetyl derivative of **1c** was then subjected to oxymercuration-demercuration reactions. Unlike **1b** and **2b**, treatment of 19-*epi*-taraxasteryl acetate (**1d**) with mercuric acetate in aqueous THF at ambient temperature followed by borohydride reduction of the resultant reaction mixture afforded two compounds **C** and **D** in the ratio of about 3 : 1. Due to extremely low yield of **1c** in the Wittig reaction, it has not been possible to prepare these compounds in amounts sufficient to carry out detailed studies on them except mass spectral analysis, which, however, suggests the isomeric structures **5a** and **5b** for the two compounds, the stereochemistry at C-20 remaining undefined. The formation of **5a** and **5b** may be explained as the result of normal oxymercuration of **1d**, which can equally form the α - and β -mercurium ions **9b** and **9a**, respectively (Scheme III). Consideration of the steric effects on the nucleophile attacking the species **9a** and **9b** suggests that the major compound (**C**) should have the stereochemistry at C-20 as shown in **5a**, while the minor product (**D**) should have the opposite stereochemistry at this centre as in **5b**.

The above investigations on **1b**, **2b** and **1d** thus provide significant information regarding steric effects on oxymercuration of olefinic compounds.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a Kofler block and are uncorrected. IR spectra were run in KBr disc in a Beckman-Infrared spectrophotometer (Model 20). ^1H nmr spectra were mostly recorded in an 80 MHz Varian CFT-20 instrument

Scheme III

in CDCl_3 solution using TMS as the internal standard, and the chemical shifts are expressed in δ_{ppm} . The ^{13}C nmr spectra were also run in the same instrument using a 20MHz oscillator in CDCl_3 and with the same internal standard. The substitution profile of carbon centres were determined by off-resonance decoupling technique (SFORD). Mass spectra were run in an AEI MS9 instrument equipped with a direct inlet system and operating at 70 eV. The figure in first bracket attached to each m/e value indicates relative intensity which is abbreviated as r.i. Silica gel (60-100 mesh) was used for column chromatography and silica gel G for tlc performed at room temperature (25-35°). All analytical samples were routinely dried over P_2O_5 at 55-138° depending on the m.p. of the compounds for 24 hr *in vacuo*. Anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was used for drying organic solvents and petrol used had b.p. 60-80°.

Attempted oxymercuration-demercuration of 1b and 2b: Taraxasterol (1a) isolated from the petrol extract of *Launaea nudicaulis*⁸ was acetylated in the usual manner to give 1b, crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH (1 : 9), m.p. 239-40°, $[\alpha]_D +94.5^\circ$ (CHCl_3). 1b was isomerised with 10% ethanolic H_2SO_4 following the previously reported method⁹ to give 2a which was acetylated with Ac_2O /py to give 2b, crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH (1 : 9), m.p. 228°, $[\alpha]_D +51.8^\circ$ (CHCl_3).

To a solution of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ (0.065 g) in H_2O (1 ml) and THF (3 ml) was added a solution of 1b (0.09 g) in THF (2 ml) at r.t. (25°) and the mixture was stirred for 5 hr. At first a yellow suspension was formed, which did not disappear even at the end of the reaction period. The reaction mixture was then treated with 5 ml of 3M NaOH followed by 15 ml of a solution of 0.5M NaBH_4 in 3M NaOH. It was stirred for about 15 min and then filtered, the residue washed with THF. The combined filtrate was saturated with NaCl and extracted with THF, dried and the solvent removed. The residue crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH (1 : 9) to give unreacted 1b (0.085 g). TLC of the total reaction product did not show any spot other than those corresponding to 1b and a trace of 1a.

Pseudo-taraxasteryl acetate (0.09 g) was also treated with $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ in aqueous THF in the above proportion and in the same manner. Treatment of the reaction mixture with alkaline NaBH_4 and working up in the above manner gave unreacted 2b (0.085 g). Here again tlc of the total reaction product did not show any spot other than those corresponding to 2b and a trace of 2a.

Both 1b (0.045 g) and 2b (0.045 g) were separately treated with $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ in THF and the mixture in each case was stirred at refluxing temperature for 2 hr. Treatment of the reaction mixture in each case with alkaline NaBH_4 followed by usual work-up gave unreacted starting material and trace of the corresponding deacetyl derivative.

Reaction of 1b and 2b with $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ in glacial HOAc: A solution of 1b (0.235 g) in HOAc (10 ml) was treated with $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ (0.15 g) dissolved

in HOAc (1 ml). The mixture was then refluxed on a magnetic stirrer for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered while hot to free it from deposited metallic mercury. The filtrate, after dilution with water, was extracted with CHCl_3 , washed, dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (100 : 1) eluate gave unchanged 1b (0.035 g). Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) afforded 2c, crystallised from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 242°, $[\alpha]_D +66.9^\circ$ (CHCl_3). Found: C, 77.50; H, 10.23. $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 77.56; H, 10.26%. ν_{max} 1220, 1240 and 1735 cm^{-1} (OAc); δ_{ppm} : 5.6, 1H, m ($>\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-$); 4.5, 2H, AB q ($-\text{CH}=\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-$);

OAc); 4.5, 1H, m obscured in the above signal ($>\text{CHOAc}$); 2.05, 6H, s ($-\text{OCOCH}_3$); 0.72-1.03 (7 C-methyls); m/e (r.i.); 526 (M^+ , 3), 484 (12), 466(99.8), 386(5), 324(12), 249(46), 216(44), 189(100), 187(99.9), 173(47), 135(99.5), 107(99.9), 95(99), 81(98) and 69(99).

In an identical manner 2b (0.05 g) was treated with $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ (0.03 g) in glacial HOAc. The reaction product was worked up as above and chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate gave unchanged 2b (0.008 g), while the petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) eluate afforded a solid (0.04 g), crystallised from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 242°. It was found to be identical in all respects with 2c.

Preparation of the triols 3a and 3b from 1b: Following the method used earlier¹⁰ for structurally similar compound, 1b (1.9 g) dissolved in a mixture (1 : 1) of dry pyridine and CHCl_3 (100 ml) was treated with OsO_4 (1 g) and the solution was kept at 20° for 7 days. Removal of solvent under reduced pressure gave a dark residue which was heated under reflux for 3 hr with benzene (45 ml), MeOH (45 ml) and a mixture of KOH (10.5 g) and mannitol (10.5 g) in EtOH (45 ml) and water (28 ml). The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was diluted with water, extracted with ether after saturating the solution with NaCl. The ether extract was dried, evaporated and the residue was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate gave 1a (0.05 g). Further elution of the column with 5% methanolic CHCl_3 gave the mixture of triols 3a and 3b (total yield 0.75 g). The mixture was then rechromatographed over alumina. The early fractions of the 5% methanolic CHCl_3 eluate, on evaporation, gave a solid which crystallised from petrol-EtOAc to give the pure less polar triol 3b ($\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_3$) as the developer. Found: C, 78.30; H, 11.33. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 78.26; H, 11.30%. ν_{max} 3400 cm^{-1} (OH); δ_{ppm} : 3.55, 2H, AB q, $J=10\text{ Hz}$ ($-\text{C}-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$); 3.2, 1H, m ($>\text{CHOH}$) and 0.75-1.05 (7 C-methyls); m/e (r.i.); 460 (M^+ , 6), 442(5.5), 429(38.9), 411(19.3), 373(25.8), 355(20), 216(17.1), 207(81.2), 205(22.5), 191(50.5), 189(100), 187(21), 81(73.5) and 69(82.9).

The later fractions of the 5% methanolic CHCl_3 eluate in the above chromatography afforded a solid which crystallised from petrol-EtOAc to give the pure more polar triol **3a** (0.69 g), m.p. 260° , R_f 0.35 with MeOH- CHCl_3 (1 : 1) as the developer. Found : C, 78.20 ; H, 11.41. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 78.26 ; H, 11.30%. ν_{max} 3400 cm^{-1} (OH) ;

δ_{ppm} : 3.35, 2H, AB q, $J=10\text{ Hz}$ ($-\text{C}-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$) ;
 3.15, 1H, m ($>\text{CHOH}$) and 0.7-1.0 (7 C-methyls) ;
 m/e (r.i.) : 460 (M^+ , 5), 442(5), 429(37), 411(19),
 373(26), 355(19), 216(17.5), 207(82), 205(23.5),
 191(51.1), 189(100), 187(21.2), 81(73.4) and
 69(81.8).

Formation of the norketone 4a : The mixture of the triols **3a** and **3b** (0.75 g) dissolved in EtOH (320 ml) was treated with a solution of sodium metaperiodate (0.55 g) in water (5.5 ml). The mixture was kept at 20° for 16 hr. EtOH was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was treated with water (30 ml), extracted with ether and dried. Removal of solvent gave a solid (0.47 g) which on repeated crystallisations from petrol-EtOAc afforded pure **4a**, m.p. 262° ; R_f 0.4 with petrol-EtOAc (4 : 1) as the developer. Found : C, 81.2 ; H, 11.24. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 81.30 ; H, 11.21%. ν_{max} 3380 (OH) and 1700 (>C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_{ppm} : 3.15 1H, m ($>\text{CHOH}$) ;

2.40, 3H, m ($\text{Me}-\text{CH}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$) ; 1.1, 3H
 d, $J=7\text{ Hz}$ ($\text{Me}-\text{CH}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-$) and 0.71-1.0 (6 C-meth-

yls) ; m/e (r.i.) : 428 (M^+ , 17.5), 410(63.5), 395
 (40.9), 367(25.1), 341(10.7), 328(29.3), 259(10.8),
 207(41), 189(100), 136(77.8), 135(76.3), 123(60.6),
 121(64.7), 109(55.5), 95(77.9), 81(65.9) and
 69(61.8).

Epimerisation of 4a : A solution of **4a** (0.35 g) in CHCl_3 was adsorbed on Brockmann alumina in a column and kept for 3 days. The material was then eluted with CHCl_3 . Removal of solvent gave a solid (0.34 g) which on repeated crystallisations from petrol-EtOAc afforded a microcrystalline material, m.p. 242° , having R_f value same as that of **4a**. The ir, pmr. and mass spectra of this material were very similar to those of **4a**. It was shown to be a mixture of **4a** and **4b** by comparison of its ^{13}C nmr spectral data with those of pure **4a**.

Wittig reaction on the mixture of 4a and 4b : A solution of equimolecular amounts of $\phi_3\text{P}$ (7.86 g) and CH_2I (4.26 g) in perfectly dry CHCl_3 (25 ml) was refluxed for 1 hr. Removal of solvent left an oily residue which was treated with dry ether when a gummy solid separated out. The crude solid was crystallised from Et₂O-MeOH to give pure methyl-triphenylphosphonium iodide (4.5 g), m.p. $181-83^\circ$. It was dried in vacuum desiccator.

A 50 ml r.b. flask equipped with a dropping funnel (with pressure-equaliser device), a reflux

condenser and a nitrogen-inlet tube was placed on a magnetic stirrer. The whole system was repeatedly flushed with dry, oxygen-free nitrogen. Oil-free NaH (0.75 g) was introduced into the flask and to it was added dry DMSO (6 ml) through the dropping funnel. The mixture was heated at $75-80^\circ$ for 2 hr in dry, oxygen-free nitrogen atmosphere until the evolution of hydrogen ceased. The resultant solution was then cooled in ice-bath and to this was added dropwise through the dropping funnel a solution of

$\phi_3\text{PCH}_2\text{I}$ (2 g) in DMSO (10 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. To this was added dropwise from the dropping funnel a solution of 0.25 g of the mixture of **4a** and **4b** in DMSO (30 ml). The reaction mixture was then heated at $60-70^\circ$ for 40 hr. The product was decomposed with ice-cold water (saturated with NaCl), extracted with ether, washed with brine and dried. Removal of solvent gave a residue which was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (20 : 1) eluate gave a mixture of **1a** and **1c** (0.03 g). The mixture was rechromatographed. The early fractions of petrol-EtOAc (25 : 1) gave **1a** (0.011 g), R_f 0.45 in petrol-EtOAc (6 : 1) as the developer. The later fractions of the same eluate gave pure **1c**, (0.017 g), R_f 0.40 in petrol-EtOAc (6 : 1) as the developer. Found : C, 84.48 ; H, 11.78. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.51 ; H, 11.73%. δ_{ppm} : 4.7, 2H, m ($-\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$) ; 3.06, 1H, m ($>\text{CHOH}$) and 0.77-1.2

(7 C-methyls) ; m/e (r.i.) : 426(M^+ , 12.3), 357(4.6),
 218(12.3), 207(53.8), 189(100), 149(95), 109(99.1),
 107(90), 81(98.9) and 69(95).

Oxymercuration-demercuration of 1d : **1c** (0.012 g) was acetylated with $\text{Ac}_2\text{O/py}$ in the usual manner. The product crystallised from MeOH- CHCl_3 (9 : 1) to give **1d**, m.p. 210° . To a solution of 0.007 g of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ in 0.2 ml water was added 0.8 ml THF, when a yellow suspension was formed. To this was added a solution of **1d** (0.01 g) in THF (2 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 1 hr. Within a few minutes the yellow suspension became almost clear. The reaction mixture was treated with 1 ml of 3M NaOH followed by 3 ml solution of 0.5M NaBH_4 in 3M NaOH, and stirred for 15 min. The mass was filtered and the filtrate was saturated with NaCl, extracted with THF and dried. Removal of solvent gave a white residue which was chromatographed. The early fractions of petrol-EtOAc (10:1) eluate gave **5b** (0.002 g), crystallised from MeOH- CHCl_3 (9 : 1), m.p. 200° , R_f 0.5 in petrol-EtOAc (3 : 1) as the developer. M/e (r.i.) : 486(M^+ , 4), 468(10.2), 207(100), 189(94.5), 135(95.3), 123(50.4), 121(40.5), 109(99.1) and 107(65.1).

The later fractions of the petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate in the above chromatography afforded **5a** (0.006 g), crystallised from MeOH- CHCl_3 (9 : 1), m.p. 170° , R_f 0.4 in petrol-EtOAc (3 : 1) as the developer. M/e (r.i.) : 486(M^+ , 4.5), 468(15.8), 207(98.1), 189(100), 135(93.1), 123(55.5), 121(45.5), 109(98.1) and 107(68.1).

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